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Epstein Barr virus is the cause of multiple myeloma

Research article

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Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

The first well-documented case of Multiple myeloma (MM) has been reported in 1844 by Samuel Solly. Epstein–Barr virus (EBV) has been discovered 1964 by Michael Anthony Epstein, Bert Geoffrey Achong and Yvonne M. Barr. In this paper, the causal relationship between EBV and MM has been investigated.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

New statistical methods were used.

RESULTS:

Without EBV infection, no MM. If EBV infection of human bone marrow, then MM.

CONCLUSION:

EBV is the cause of MM.

Keywords:

Epstein–Barr virus; Multiple myeloma; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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1. Introduction

Human plasma cells reside in human bone marrow and are mature antibody-producing B cells which are essential for maintaining humoral immunity. An aggressive plasma cell dyscrasia can occur. Multiple myeloma (MM) is such a plasma cell disorder which develops almost exclusively in the bone marrow.¹ MM is characterized by a monoclonal proliferation of human plasma cells and results in the production of monoclonal antibody and end-organ damage.^{2,3} In 2018, Global Cancer Observatory (GLOBOCAN) statistics estimated that there are about 160,000 cases of MM globally, accounting for about 0.9% of all cancer diagnoses.⁴ while about 106,000 people globally perished of MM, accounting for 1.1% of all cancer deaths.⁵ The cumulative risk from birth to 74 of being diagnosed with MM is 0.17% among women and 0.24% among men.⁶ The survival of humans suffering from MM is also dependent upon the stage of MM at diagnosis.^{7,8} The 5-year survival rate for those with localized MM disease (which only accounts for 5% of all cases) is about 74.8% whereas the 5-year survival rate for those affected with systematic MM (the remaining 95% of diagnoses) is about 52.9%.⁹ The influence of risk factors^{10,11} like age, sex, race, family history, and other on MM have been discussed in literature. Despite all this, the cause or even a cause¹² of this disease remains completely in the dark. Meanwhile, there is some slight evidence, that Non-Hodgkin lymphoma (NHL) are Epstein Barr virus determined.¹³ Epstein–Barr virus (EBV), a double-stranded deoxyribonucleic

¹Brigle K, Rogers B. Pathobiology and Diagnosis of Multiple Myeloma. *Semin Oncol Nurs.* 2017 Aug;33(3):225-236. doi: 10.1016/j.soncn.2017.05.012. Epub 2017 Jul 5. PMID: 28688533.

²Jurczyszyn A., Suska A. Multiple Myeloma. *Encycl. Biomed. Gerontol.* 2019;2:461–478. doi: 10.1016/b978-0-12-801238-3.11412-6.

³Padala SA, Barsouk A, Barsouk A, Rawla P, Vakiti A, Kolhe R, Kota V, Ajebo GH. Epidemiology, Staging, and Management of Multiple Myeloma. *Med Sci (Basel).* 2021 Jan 20;9(1):3. doi: 10.3390/medsci9010003. PMID: 33498356; PMCID: PMC7838784.

⁴Global Cancer Observatory: Cancer Today. Lyon, France: International Agency for Research on Cancer.; Available online: <https://gco.iarc.fr/today>

⁵ibidem

⁶Bray F, Ferlay J, Soerjomataram I, Siegel RL, Torre LA, Jemal A. Global cancer statistics 2018: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries. *CA Cancer J Clin.* 2018 Nov;68(6):394-424. doi: 10.3322/caac.21492. Epub 2018 Sep 12. Erratum in: *CA Cancer J Clin.* 2020 Jul;70(4):313. PMID: 30207593.

⁷Durie BG, Salmon SE. A clinical staging system for multiple myeloma. Correlation of measured myeloma cell mass with presenting clinical features, response to treatment, and survival. *Cancer.* 1975 Sep;36(3):842-54. doi: 10.1002/1097-0142(197509)36:3;842::aid-cnrc2820360303;3.0.co;2-u. PMID: 1182674.

⁸Palumbo A, Avet-Loiseau H, Oliva S, Lokhorst HM, Goldschmidt H, Rosinol L, Richardson P, Caltagirone S, Lahuerta JJ, Facon T, Bringhen S, Gay F, Attal M, Passera R, Spencer A, Offidani M, Kumar S, Musto P, Lonial S, Petrucci MT, Orłowski RZ, Zamagni E, Morgan G, Dimopoulos MA, Durie BG, Anderson KC, Sonneveld P, San Miguel J, Cavo M, Rajkumar SV, Moreau P. Revised International Staging System for Multiple Myeloma: A Report From International Myeloma Working Group. *J Clin Oncol.* 2015 Sep 10;33(26):2863-9. doi: 10.1200/JCO.2015.61.2267. Epub 2015 Aug 3. PMID: 26240224; PMCID: PMC4846284.

⁹Howlander N., Noone A.M., Krapcho M., Miller D., Brest A., Yu M., Ruhl J., Tatalovich Z., Mariotto A., Lewis D.R., et al. SEER Cancer Statistics Review 1975–2016. National Cancer Institute; Bethesda, MD, USA: 2019.

¹⁰Sergentanis TN, Zagouri F, Tsilimidos G, Tsagianni A, Tseliou M, Dimopoulos MA, Psaltopoulou T. Risk Factors for Multiple Myeloma: A Systematic Review of Meta-Analyses. *Clin Lymphoma Myeloma Leuk.* 2015 Oct;15(10):563-77.e1-3. doi: 10.1016/j.clml.2015.06.003. Epub 2015 Jun 19. PMID: 26294217.

¹¹Corre J, Munshi NC, Avet-Loiseau H. Risk factors in multiple myeloma: is it time for a revision? *Blood.* 2021 Jan 7;137(1):16-19. doi: 10.1182/blood.2019004309. PMID: 33024991; PMCID: PMC7808011.

¹²Blimark C, Holmberg E, Mellqvist UH, Landgren O, Björkholm M, Hultcrantz M, Kjellander C, Turesson I, Kristinsson SY. Multiple myeloma and infections: a population-based study on 9253 multiple myeloma patients. *Haematologica.* 2015 Jan;100(1):107-13. doi: 10.3324/haematol.2014.107714. Epub 2014 Oct 24. PMID: 25344526; PMCID: PMC4281323.

¹³Barukčić, Ilija. (2022). Without Epstein Barr virus infection, no non Hodgkin lymphoma. *Causation*, 17(12), 5–131. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6791972>

acid (DNA)¹⁴ human γ -herpes virus 4 (HHV4)¹⁵, with a 170-kb-large genome¹⁶ which encodes for various proteins and non-coding RNAs has been discovered 1964 by Michael Anthony Epstein, Bert Geoffrey Achong and Yvonne M. Barr.¹⁷ After a generally asymptomatic primary EBV infection of mainly B-cells and epithelial cells usually during childhood, EBV resides latently¹⁸ in resting B¹⁹ cells for a lifetime,²⁰ the resting B cells are one site of long-term latent persistence for EBV. However, under normal circumstances, an EBV infection is controlled by human immune system and individuals carrying EBV do not suffer from the viral infection. We have reasons to believe that up to 95% of the adult population worldwide²¹ are infected by EBV at some time during their life span. The increase of EBV seroprevalence with age is well documented (see table 1) and results from cumulative exposure to EBV throughout life.

Table 1. EBV seroprevalence increases with age (Cui et al., 2018, China).

Age y=year	EBV VCA IgG Pos no. (%)	EBV EBNA1 IgG Pos no. (%)	EBV VCA IgM Pos no. (%)	EBV VCA IgA Pos no. (%)	EB EA/D IgA Pos no. (%)
0–5y	283 (66.59)	141 (58.51)	65 (14.57)	52 (14.57)	26 (7.12)
6–10y	431 (84.34)	226 (78.75)	55 (10.24)	93 (22.79)	39 (9.18)
11–20y	784 (92.89)	413 (86.95)	123 (10.41)	178 (23.73)	95 (12.20)
21–30y	809 (98.54)	271 (95.43)	88 (6.25)	192 (26.10)	120 (15.33)
31–40y	853 (98.84)	203 (94.86)	40 (3.06)	219 (22.71)	123 (11.80)
41–50y	892 (99.78)	202 (97.57)	36 (2.76)	282 (22.54)	171 (13.13)
51–60y	957 (99.79)	248 (96.12)	37 (2.62)	301 (27.54)	184 (15.79)
61–101y	902 (99.01)	258 (93.82)	29 (2.03)	258 (33.42)	146 (18.36)

In this publication, we would like to address the issue of causality between EBV and MM in some more detail.

¹⁴James Dewey Watson, Francis Harry Compton Crick. Molecular structure of nucleic acids; a structure for deoxyribose nucleic acid. *Nature*. 1953 Apr 25;171(4356):737-8. doi: 10.1038/171737a0. PMID: 13054692.

¹⁵Walker PJ, Siddell SG, Lefkowitz EJ, Mushegian AR, Adriaenssens EM, Alfenas-Zerbini P, Davison AJ, Dempsey DM, Dutilh BE, García ML, Harrach B, Harrison RL, Hendrickson RC, Junglen S, Knowles NJ, Krupovic M, Kuhn JH, Lambert AJ, Łobocka M, Nibert ML, Oksanen HM, Orton RJ, Robertson DL, Rubino L, Sabanadzovic S, Simmonds P, Smith DB, Suzuki N, Van Dooerslaer K, Vandamme AM, Varsani A, Zerbini FM. Changes to virus taxonomy and to the International Code of Virus Classification and Nomenclature ratified by the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses (2021). *Arch Virol*. 2021 Sep;166(9):2633-2648. doi: 10.1007/s00705-021-05156-1. PMID: 34231026.

¹⁶Feederle R, Klinke O, Kutikhin A, Poirey R, Tsai MH, Delecluse HJ. Epstein-Barr Virus: From the Detection of Sequence Polymorphisms to the Recognition of Viral Types. *Curr Top Microbiol Immunol*. 2015;390(Pt 1):119-48. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-228228_7. PMID: 26424646.

¹⁷Michael Anthony Epstein, Bert Geoffrey Achong, Yvonne M. Barr. Virus Particles in Cultured Lymphoblasts from Burkitt's Lymphoma. *Lancet*. 1964 Mar 28;1(7335):702-3. doi: 10.1016/s0140-6736(64)91524-7. PMID: 14107961.

¹⁸Babcock GJ, Decker LL, Volk M, Thorley-Lawson DA. EBV persistence in memory B cells in vivo. *Immunity*. 1998 Sep;9(3):395-404. doi: 10.1016/s1074-7613(00)80622-6. PMID: 9768759.

¹⁹Miyashita EM, Yang B, Babcock GJ, Thorley-Lawson DA. Identification of the site of Epstein-Barr virus persistence in vivo as a resting B cell. *J Virol*. 1997 Jul;71(7):4882-91. doi: 10.1128/JVI.71.7.4882-4891.1997. Erratum in: *J Virol* 1998 Nov;72(11):9419. PMID: 9188550; PMCID: PMC191718.

²⁰Amon W, Farrell PJ. Reactivation of Epstein-Barr virus from latency. *Rev Med Virol*. 2005 May-Jun;15(3):149-56. doi: 10.1002/rmv.456. PMID: 15546128.

²¹Cui J, Yan W, Xu S, Wang Q, Zhang W, Liu W, Ni A. Anti-Epstein-Barr virus antibodies in Beijing during 2013-2017: What we have found in the different patients. *PLoS One*. 2018 Mar 1;13(3):e0193171. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0193171. PMID: 29494658; PMCID: PMC5832223.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

2.1.1. The study of Mameli et al., 2017, Italy.

Monoclonal gammopathy of undetermined significance (MGUS) is defined as < 10% clonal plasma cells (PCs) in the bone marrow (BM), a serum M protein < 30 g/l and, most importantly, the absence of end-organ damage (CRAB: hypercalcemia, renal insufficiency, anemia, bone lesions) that can be attributed to the PC proliferative disorder. It is necessary that all three criteria must be met.²² MGUS with the characteristic of progression into multiple myeloma is a premalignant disorder. Mameli et al.²³ performed a case–control study on samples from 34 MM patients, 25 subjects with MGUS and 25 age and sex matched healthy controls (HC), while the diagnosis of MM and MGUS was performed according to international guidelines.²⁴ Mameli et al. found that 23/25 MGUS sera, 22/25 MM sera and 15/25 HCs sera were positive by ELISA for Epstein-Barr nuclear antigen 1 (EBNA-1) immunoglobulin (IgG) antibodies to EBV. EBNA-1 EBV IgG antibodies provide evidence of EBV positivity of a subject.

²²International Myeloma Working Group. Criteria for the classification of monoclonal gammopathies, multiple myeloma and related disorders: a report of the International Myeloma Working Group. *Br J Haematol.* 2003 Jun;121(5):749-57. PMID: 12780789.

²³Mameli G, Fozza C, Niegowska M, Corda G, Ruda MF, Barraqueddu F, Dessì L, Podda L, Dore F, Sechi LA. Epstein-Barr virus infection is associated to patients with multiple myeloma and monoclonal gammopathy of undetermined significance. *Leuk Lymphoma.* 2017 Feb;58(2):466-469. doi: 10.1080/10428194.2016.1190976. Epub 2016 Jun 7. PMID: 27268403.

²⁴Kyle RA, Durie BG, Rajkumar SV, Landgren O, Blade J, Merlini G, Kröger N, Einsele H, Vesole DH, Dimopoulos M, San Miguel J, Avet-Loiseau H, Hajek R, Chen WM, Anderson KC, Ludwig H, Sonneveld P, Pavlovsky S, Palumbo A, Richardson PG, Barlogie B, Greipp P, Vescio R, Turesson I, Westin J, Boccadoro M; International Myeloma Working Group. Monoclonal gammopathy of undetermined significance (MGUS) and smoldering (asymptomatic) multiple myeloma: IMWG consensus perspectives risk factors for progression and guidelines for monitoring and management. *Leukemia.* 2010 Jun;24(6):1121-7. doi: 10.1038/leu.2010.60. Epub 2010 Apr 22. PMID: 20410922; PMCID: PMC7020664.

Table 2. EBV EBNA-1 IgG and MGUS (Study of Mameli et al., 2017).

		MGUS		
		YES	NO	
EBV EBNA-1 IgG	YES	23	15	38
	NO	2	10	12
		25	25	50

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = +0,37463432$
P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00903844
p (SINE) = 0,96000000
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) > 0,92000000
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) > 0,83333333

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00903844
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 0,33
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0,16
P Value (SINE) = 0,03921056

PROPORTIONS.

(a/A) × 100 = (23 / 38) × 100 = 60,53 %
(b/A) × 100 = (15 / 38) × 100 = 39,47 %
(c/ not A) × 100 = (2 / 12) × 100 = 16,67 %
(d/ not A) × 100 = (10 / 12) × 100 = 83,33 %
(a/B) × 100 = (23 / 25) × 100 = 92,00 %
(c/B) × 100 = (2 / 25) × 100 = 8,00 %
(b/ not B) × 100 = (15 / 25) × 100 = 60,00 %
(d/ not B) × 100 = (10 / 25) × 100 = 40,00 %
(A/N) × 100 = (38 / 50) × 100 = 76,00 %
(not A/N) × 100 = (12 / 50) × 100 = 24,00 %
(B/N) × 100 = (25 / 50) × 100 = 50,00 %
(not B/N) × 100 = (25 / 50) × 100 = 50,00 %

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.**RELATIVE RISK (RR).**

RR (necessary condition) = 3,63157895
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,53333333

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 7,66666667
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,21052632

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,26000000
p(IOI)= 0,26000000

The study design of the study of Mameli et al. is very unfair (p(IOU)= 0,26). Mameli et al.'s study is based on a prevalence of EBV in the population as (b/ not B) × 100 = (15 / 25) × 100 = 60,00 %, what is too low in the age group studied. As a consequence, the relationship between EBV and MGUS is much stronger than suggested by the study of Mameli et al. Nonetheless, Mameli et al. provided evidence of the relationship **without** EBV infection, **no** MGUS (P Value = 0,00903844).

Table 3. EBV EBNA-1 IgG and Multiple myeloma (Study of Mameli et al., 2017).

		Multiple myeloma		
		YES	NO	
EBV EBNA-1 IgG	YES	22	15	37
	NO	3	10	13
		25	25	50

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,31917253$
P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,02533552
p (SINE) = 0,94000000
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) > 0,88000000
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) > 0,76923077

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,02533552
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 0,69
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0,36
P Value (SINE) = 0,05823547

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/A) \times 100 = (22 / 37) \times 100 = 59,46 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (15 / 37) \times 100 = 40,54 \%$
 $(c/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (3 / 13) \times 100 = 23,08 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (10 / 13) \times 100 = 76,92 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (22 / 25) \times 100 = 88,00 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (3 / 25) \times 100 = 12,00 \%$
 $(b/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (15 / 25) \times 100 = 60,00 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (10 / 25) \times 100 = 40,00 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (37 / 50) \times 100 = 74,00 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (13 / 50) \times 100 = 26,00 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (25 / 50) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (25 / 50) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.**RELATIVE RISK (RR).**

RR (necessary condition) = 2,57657658
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,46666667

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 4,88888889
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,18918919

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,24000000
p(IOI)= 0,24000000

2.1.2. The study of Mameli et al. , 2017 (Fair study design; Fictive data)

The data published by Mameli et al. impress with a $p(\text{IOU}) = 0$ (Barukčić, 2019a) in the negative. The study design of this study can be considered more or less as unfair and potentially biased. However, the study design of a study which is going to investigate the necessary condition or the sufficient condition or the necessary and sufficient condition relationship should assure as much as possible the condition ²⁵ $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{a}_t) = \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{d}_t)$ or that $\text{IOU}(\text{Condition}_t, \text{Conditioned}_t) = 0$. We assume a prevalence of 0,6 and $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{a}_t) = \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{d}_t) = 22$. Under these conditions, the sample size of the control group, denoted as $E(\underline{B}_t)$, is given as ²⁶

$$E(\underline{B}_t) = \frac{E(a_t)}{(1 - p_{\text{prevalence}}(A_t))} = \frac{22}{(1 - p_{\text{prevalence}}(0,6))} = 55 \quad (1)$$

The data of Mameli et al. have been re-calculated under the assumptions before.

²⁵Barukčić, Ilija. (2022). Conditions and study design. *Causation*, 18(1), 5–99.

²⁶Barukčić, Ilija. (2023). Cytomegalovirus and lung cancer - a causal relationship?. *Causation*, 18(11), 5–33. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7602865>

Table 4. EBV EBNA-1 IgG and Multiple myeloma (Study of Mameli et al., 2017 (Fictive data)).

		Multiple myeloma		
		YES	NO	
EBV EBNA-1 IgG	YES	22	33	55
	NO	3	22	25
		25	55	80

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,28000000$
P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00995338
p (SINE) = 0,96250000
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) > 0,88000000
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) > 0,88000000

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00995338
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 0,36
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0,36
P Value (SINE) = 0,03680558

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/A) \times 100 = (22 / 55) \times 100 = 40,00 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (33 / 55) \times 100 = 60,00 \%$
 $(c/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (3 / 25) \times 100 = 12,00 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (22 / 25) \times 100 = 88,00 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (22 / 25) \times 100 = 88,00 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (3 / 25) \times 100 = 12,00 \%$
 $(b/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (33 / 55) \times 100 = 60,00 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (22 / 55) \times 100 = 40,00 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (55 / 80) \times 100 = 68,75 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (25 / 80) \times 100 = 31,25 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (25 / 80) \times 100 = 31,25 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (55 / 80) \times 100 = 68,75 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.**RELATIVE RISK (RR).**

RR (necessary condition) = 3,33333333
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,46666667

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 4,88888889
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,28000000

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,00000000
p(IOI)= 0,37500000

Under fair study conditions, the relationship between EBV and MM is much stronger, than suggested by the study of Mameli et al. However, the necessary condition relationship is not equal to 1, but has to be equal to 1. This fact has something to do with the sensitivity and the specificity of the laboratory kit used, has to do with the accuracy of the diagnosis and with other factors.

2.1.3. The study of Mohammad Hadi Sadeghian, 2011, Iran.

Mohammad Hadi Sadeghian et al. ²⁷ conducted a case-control study on 60 paraffin-embedded bone marrow biopsies (30 normal bone marrow specimens and 30 multiple myeloma) to investigate whether there is a relationship between MM and EBV by the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) method. Sadeghian et al. detected deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) of EBV in 10/30 patients of the case group and 3/30 subjects of the control group.

²⁷Sadeghian MH, Ayatollahi H, Keramati MR, Memar B, Jamedar SA, Avval MM, Sheikhi M, Shaghayegh G. The association of Epstein-Barr virus infection with multiple myeloma. *Indian J Pathol Microbiol.* 2011 Oct-Dec;54(4):720-4. doi: 10.4103/0377-4929.91504. PMID: 22234097.

Table 5. EBV DNA and Multiple myeloma (Study of Sadeghian et al., 2011).

		Multiple myeloma		
		YES	NO	
EBV DNA	YES	10	3	13
	NO	20	27	47
		30	30	60

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = +0,28318969$
P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,02873314
p (IMP) = 0,95
p (IMP) approx.= 1-(b/A) > 0,76923077
p (IMP) approx.= 1-(b/(Not B)) > 0,90000000

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,02873314
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP— A_t) = 0,69
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP— Not B_t) = 0,30
P Value (IMP) = 0,04877058

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/A) \times 100 = (10 / 13) \times 100 = 76,92 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (3 / 13) \times 100 = 23,08 \%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (20 / 47) \times 100 = 42,55 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (27 / 47) \times 100 = 57,45 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (10 / 30) \times 100 = 33,33 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (20 / 30) \times 100 = 66,67 \%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (3 / 30) \times 100 = 10,00 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (27 / 30) \times 100 = 90,00 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (13 / 60) \times 100 = 21,67 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (47 / 60) \times 100 = 78,33 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (30 / 60) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (30 / 60) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.**RELATIVE RISK (RR).**

RR (necessary condition) = 1,80769231
RR (sufficient condition) = 3,33333333

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 4,50000000
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,53846154

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,28333333
p(IOI)= 0,28333333

The measure RR (sufficient condition) = 3,33333333 indicates a significant sufficient condition relationship while the study design is very unfair (p(IOU)= 0,28333333).

2.2. Methods

Avoiding and treatment of logical fallacies addresses one of the most important aspects of any scientific inquiry. Sometimes logically sound definitions are of great help in order to enable us to properly infer **from something known to something unknown**. It also goes without any need of further saying that a definition as such should be logically consistent and correct. However, theoretically, circumstances might exist under which it is required to *deal with erroneous definitions*²⁸ too.

2.2.1. Conditio sine qua non relationship

The probability of the necessary condition relationship $p(\text{SINE})$ has been calculated (Barukčić, 2021a,b) and tested for statistical significance. The chi-square goodness of fit test $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | B)$ and $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | \underline{A})$ with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit the theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship in the population. Additionally, the P Value has been calculated approximately (see also Barukčić, 2019b). The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2016, 2020, 2021b) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events. The cumulative, right-tailed hyper-geometric (Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided right-tailed significance of the causal relationship k . As known, a negative causal relationship ($k < 0$) would contradict a necessary condition relationship and vice versa.

2.2.2. Conditio per quam relationship

The probability of the sufficient condition relationship $p(\text{IMP})$ has been calculated (Barukčić, 2021a,b, 2022) and tested for statistical significance. The chi-square goodness of fit test $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | A)$ and $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | \underline{B})$ with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit the theoretical distribution of an sufficient condition relationship in the population. Additionally, the P Value has been calculated approximately (see also Barukčić, 2019b). The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2016, 2020, 2021b) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events. The cumulative, right-tailed hyper-geometric (Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided right-tailed significance of the causal relationship k . As known, a negative causal relationship would contradict a sufficient condition relationship and vice versa.

2.2.3. Hyper-geometric distribution

In general, the probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable X is called a hyper-geometric distribution. In contrast to the binomial distribution, the hyper-geometric distribution is

²⁸Strobino, Riccardo, "Ibn Sina's Logic", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Fall 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2018/entries/ibn-sina-logic/>.

characterised by the lack of replacements. In this context, let N denote the population size, let A denote the number of success in the population, let B denote the number of draws (i.e. quantity drawn in each trial), let a itself denote the number of observed successes.

Table 6. Hyper-geometric random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	a	b	A
	FALSE	c	d	\underline{A}
		B	\underline{B}	N

With this in mind, the probability mass function of the hyper-geometric distribution (see Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899), denoted as $p(X = a)$, is defined as

$$p(X = a) = \frac{\binom{A}{a} \binom{N-A}{B-a}}{\binom{N}{B}} = \frac{\binom{B}{a} \binom{N-B}{A-a}}{\binom{N}{A}} \quad (2)$$

The hyper-geometric distribution, a probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable, has several properties which unfortunately cannot be discussed in detail here. A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some specified lower limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{i=a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (3)$$

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is less than or equal to some specified upper limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=a} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (4)$$

2.2.4. Fisher's exact test

Fisher's exact test proposed by Fisher (1934) in the fifth edition of *Statistical Methods for Research Workers* (see Fisher, 1934, pp. 99-103) is a statistical significance test which is often used in the analysis of contingency tables while applying the hyper-geometric distribution²⁹. This statistical methodology opens up the possibility to calculate the significance of the deviation from a null hypothesis (e.g., P Value) exactly. Strangely enough, it is common practice to use Fisher's exact test (see also Fisher, 1935) for a sample which is very small. However, it is necessary to point out that Fisher's exact test is valid for all sample sizes without any restriction. Fisher's Exact Test is using the following null and alternative hypotheses:

H0: (null hypothesis)

The two random variables are independent.

H1: (alternative hypothesis)

The two random variables are not independent.

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability denotes whether a hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some specified lower limit and less than or equal to some specified upper limit. The P Value of an one-sided right tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{i=a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (5)$$

The P Value of an one-sided left tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=a} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (6)$$

2.2.5. The Chi-square goodness of fit test

The χ^2 distribution is one of the most versatile distributions in applied statistics. Historically, the χ^2 distribution has been described by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert (see Helmert, 1876). Later, the χ^2 distribution has been rediscovered by Karl Pearson (see Pearson, 1900) in the context of a goodness of fit test. The Chi-square goodness of fit test checks the agreement or conformity or consistency between a hypothetical or a theoretical distribution given in a population and a sample distribution drawn from such a population. Karl Pearson's approximate formula for calculating a Chi-square statistic may be shown schematically as:

²⁹Kim HY. Statistical notes for clinical researchers: Chi-squared test and Fisher's exact test. *Restor Dent Endod.* 2017 May;42(2):152-155. doi: 10.5395/rde.2017.42.2.152. Epub 2017 Mar 30. PMID: 28503482; PMCID: PMC5426219.

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{(\text{Observed}_t - E(\text{Observed}_t))^2}{E(\text{Observed}_t)} \quad (7)$$

Some author prefer the use of Yate's correction for continuity (see [Yates, 1934](#)) when there is one degree of freedom.

Example

Let us illustrate the Chi-square goodness of fit test by an example. A random sample of 100 people with 44 men and 56 women is drawn from a certain population. It is assumed that men and women are equal in frequency in the population. The theoretical frequencies of 50 men and 50 women is compared with the observed number of men and women.

Bernoulli trial t	Event	Observed O_t	Expected $E(O_t)$	$(O_t - E(O_t))^2$	$(O_t - E(O_t))^2 / E(O_t)$
1	Men	44	50	36	0.72
2	Women	56	50	36	0.72
Rows = 2		Sample size =	100	Chi-square =	1.44

There are rows - 1 = 2 - 1 = 1 degree of freedom and for $\alpha = 5$ percent level of significance, the rejection region is $\chi^2 \geq 3.84$. A $\chi^2 = 1.44$ is less than 3.84 and not significant. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis: the sample distribution is consistent with a theoretical distribution given in population. In other words, men and women are more or less equal in frequency in the population. In the case of a necessary condition relationship (SINE), our hypotheses could be:

$$H_0: p(\text{SINE}) \geq 1 \text{ vs. } H_A: p(\text{SINE}) < 1$$

However, a probability cannot be greater than 1. Therefore, the hypotheses are more precisely

$$H_0: p(\text{SINE}) = 1 \text{ vs. } H_A: p(\text{SINE}) < 1$$

Accepting H_0 is equivalent with rejecting H_A and vice versa. Accepting H_A is equivalent with rejecting H_0 . Assumed that the degree of freedom is 1 and for $\alpha = 5$ percent level of significance, the rejection region is $\chi^2 \geq 3.84$. A χ^2 of a necessary condition relationship which is less than 3.84 is not significant. Therefore, we would have to accept the null hypothesis: a sample distribution would be consistent with a theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship given in population. However, Chi-square like any statistics has its limitations. The Chi-square is highly sensitive to sample size. The Chi-square goodness of fit test might give inaccurate results when the sample size is to

small ($N < 50$) or too large (see [Bagozzi, 1981](#)) (G-square test). When the sample sizes are too small, Fisher's exact test of independence can be considered too.

2.2.6. The P Value of extreme events

There are circumstances where N Bernoulli trials (see [Uspensky, 1937](#), p. 45) are performed while an event X_t should occur at each single Bernoulli trial t . The probability of a single event is given as

$$p(X_t) = \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t \times p(X_t)}{X_t} \quad (8)$$

The probability of a single anti-event or non-event et cetera is given as

$$p(\bar{X}_t) = 1 - p(X_t) = 1 - \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t}{X_t} - \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - X_t \times p(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t \times (1 - p(X_t))}{X_t} = \frac{E(\bar{X}_t)}{X_t} \quad (9)$$

As soon, as the number of Bernoulli trials increases, the probability of a single event follows approximately (see [Barukčić, 2019b](#), p. 1844) as

$$p(X_t) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{E(X_t)}{N}\right)\right) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{X_t \times (1 - p(X_t))}{N}\right)\right) \quad (10)$$

Under conditions where $X_t = N$, equation 10 simplifies to

$$p(X_t) = \exp(-(1 - p(X_t))) \quad (11)$$

There are single events or relationships where the probability of an event or of a relationship is constant from trial to trial and equals $p(X_t) = 1$ in the population. Nonetheless, for many reasons, such extreme events like the necessary condition relationship, the sufficient condition relationship, the exclusion relationship et cetera does not necessarily have to be given in a sample drawn from a population too. Under these circumstances, there is a need to proof whether there is a significant difference between the sample probability or proportion and the population probability or proportion or is the difference due to chance. In other words, does the sample probability or proportion deviate significantly from the population probability or proportion which itself is equal to 1. We perform a one-sided left tailed statistical test. A probability of a single event cannot be greater than 1, therefore our hypotheses are:

$$H_0: p(X_t) \leq 0.999\ 999 \dots \text{ vs. } H_A: p(X_t) > 0.999\ 999 \dots$$

In general, the expectation value of extreme events or relationship with $p(X_t) = 1$ at every single Bernoulli trial t is $E(X) = N \times p(X_t) = N \times 1 = N$. Thus far, under circumstances where $N = E(X)$, the hypotheses before simplify to

$$H_0: E(X) \leq N-1 \text{ vs. } H_A: E(X) > N-1$$

However, it is to be noted that $N > N-1$. The cumulative distribution function is given as

$$p(E(X_t))\text{cdf} = p(X_t = 0) + p(X_t = 1) + \dots + p(X_t = (N - 1)) + p(X_t = N) = +1 \quad (12)$$

It is

$$p(E(X_t) \leq N - 1) = p(X_t = 0) + p(X_t = 1) + \dots p(X_t = (N - 1)) \quad (13)$$

and

$$p(E(X_t) > N - 1) = p(E(X_t) = N) \quad (14)$$

The P Value of a one-sided left (see [Barukčić, 2019b](#), p. 1846) tailed statistical test is given as

$$\text{P Value}_{\text{one sided left tailed}} = p(E(X_t) \leq N - 1) = 1 - p(E(X_t) > N - 1) = 1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{E(X_t)}{N}\right)\right) \quad (15)$$

We have reasons to believe that a left tailed P Value which is greater than or equal to the significance level α or P Value $\geq \alpha$, is providing some evidence to accept the null hypothesis: The sample distribution deviates significantly from the population distribution. Under such circumstances, the sample data would not support a claim that i.e. there is a significant *conditio sine qua non* relationship or *conditio per quam* relationship or exclusion relationship et cetera. However, a left tailed P Value which is less than the significance level α or P Value $< \alpha$, urges us to reject the null hypothesis and to accept the alternative hypothesis. In other words, there is no deviation of the probability found in a sample distribution from the the probability of a population distribution. It is $p(X_t) = 1$ with a certain P Value.

2.2.7. Bonferroni correction

Multiple testing at a certain level of significance α might amplify the probability of false-positive findings. In other words, the more inferences are made (on a certain data body i. e. subgroup analyses et cetera), the more likely erroneous inferences might realise. At the end, several independent or dependent statistical tests performed simultaneously (on the same data body) can induce the so called family-wise error rate (FWER) or multiple testing problem. The family-wise error rate or multiple testing problem (see [Tukey, 1994](#)) is ascribed to John Wilder Tukey (1915 – 2000), an American mathematician and statistician. The probability that at least one null hypothesis out of k null hypotheses tested is falsely rejected is no longer equal to the overall significance level α but equal to

$$\alpha_{\text{FWER}} = 1 - (1 - \alpha)^k \quad (16)$$

As a consequence, a higher significance threshold for an individual hypothesis, denoted as α_i , is demanded. Various statistical techniques have been developed to address this problem. The Bonferroni multiple-comparison correction (see [Bonferroni, 1936](#); [Dunn, 1961](#)) is one of the solutions proposed to compensate for the number of inferences being made.

Example

An investigation is testing $m = 20$ hypotheses with a desired $\alpha = 0.05$. Under these circumstances, the Bonferroni correction might be of appropriate use. Each individual hypothesis should be tested at a single level of significance α_i given as

$$\alpha_i = \frac{\alpha}{m} = \frac{0,05}{20} = 0,0025 \quad (17)$$

where m is the total number hypotheses tested and α is the overall significance level. By requiring a stricter significance threshold, **an inflation of false positive results** can be prevented. In the context of further scientific development, there have been several trials to improve the Bonferroni method. One of these attempts is the so called Rom's Method published 1990 by Rom (see [Rom, 1990](#)) himself.

2.2.8. Sample size

In scientific practice, the truth is not known from the very beginning, but often need to be discovered in arduous detail work. However, under usual circumstances, it is impossible to study an entire population. So this is more or less one of the reasons why studies are conducted on samples drawn from a population and investigated. In the course of further investigations, conclusions are drawn from samples³⁰ and generalised to the population. In this regard, a sample as such should be a perfect representative of the population studied, independent of any sample size. It comes therefore as no surprise that a larger sample size might be a better representative of a certain population and will hence provide more accurate results. However, beyond a certain point, an increase in sample size is not worth the effort. In other words, proper methods of study design and sampling should be used while the prevalence of an event within a population can be considered accurately. In this process of insight, there are some mistakes which can occur. Especially, a null hypothesis which is true can incorrectly be rejected and the either way. A null hypothesis which is false can incorrectly be accepted. However, one key aspect when designing an experiment or a clinical study et cetera, is the calculation of an appropriate sample size. A sample size is the number of experimental units or measurements (i.e. the number of patients in a medical study) et cetera needed to be included into a study in order to answer a certain research question. Therefore, an accurate pre-study calculation of the sample size³¹ is of great importance. Nonetheless, it is worthy of attention that methods to calculate the sample size which are explained in statistical textbooks in more detail are prone to errors and changes in the selected parameters can lead to significant differences in the sample size. In fact, our experience so far has taught us, that a sample size which is too small, is tending to make it impossible to detect any difference or effect. In complete contrast to a small sample size, a sample that is larger than necessary might be a better representative of a certain population and may provide more accurate results. However, beyond a certain point, a sample that is too large may amplify differences and induce a waste of time and money. Thus far, are large studies really more reliable than smaller studies, are smaller studies completely worthless? Despite of all the incontestable benefits of studies with a large sample size, a variety of biases³² of studies with large sample size like measurement error, aggregation error, sampling error, multiple comparisons errors et cetera have been identified. In point of fact, studies with a large sample size can magnify the bias associated with error resulting from study design or sampling an so on. The issue of sample size is more or less not as simple as is often desired or assumed. Alongside undeniable scientific progress supported by studies, there are shortcomings and obvious delays and a particular caution and constant

³⁰Faber J, Fonseca LM. How sample size influences research outcomes. *Dental Press J Orthod.* 2014 Jul-Aug;19(4):27-9. doi: 10.1590/2176-9451.19.4.027-029.ebo. PMID: 25279518; PMCID: PMC4296634.

³¹Hickey GL, Grant SW, Dunning J, Siepe M. Statistical primer: sample size and power calculations-why, when and how? *Eur J Cardiothorac Surg.* 2018 Jul 1;54(1):4-9. doi: 10.1093/ejcts/ezy169. PMID: 29757369; PMCID: PMC6005113.

³²Kaplan RM, Chambers DA, Glasgow RE. Big data and large sample size: a cautionary note on the potential for bias. *Clin Transl Sci.* 2014 Aug;7(4):342-6. doi: 10.1111/cts.12178. Epub 2014 Jul 15. PMID: 25043853; PMCID: PMC5439816.

watchfulness and reserve is necessary, independently of the sample size of a study. In principle, even studies with a small sample size can play an important role in helping us recognise a certain relationship between events. Thus far and for illustration purposes only, let us suppose that a small study is investigating the relationship between gaseous oxygen and human being alive. Only three subjects were investigated, the following data were obtained and published.

Table 7. Gaseous oxygen and human being alive

		Human being alive B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen A_t	TRUE	1	1	2
	FALSE	0	1	1
		1	2	3

Are the results of such a study completely irrelevant? Under normal circumstances, our confidence into a relationship identified is running high, parallel with an increasing sample size. In contrast to a very large sample size, even a study with a very small sample size ($N = 3$) or even one single study is capable of identifying a fundamental relationship i.e. between gaseous oxygen and human life, it depends as always on the concrete circumstances. Human experience teaches us however that the relationship between gaseous oxygen and human life as established before is true even if the sample size of the study presented is very small. As is well known, it is rarely possible to study the entire population. Nonetheless, further studies despite a larger sample size must be able to confirm the relationship established before in principle, independently of any potential difficulties.

Type I Error (Alpha)

The type I error is also called alpha or the significance level or the P Value and represents the chance or the probability to decide that two groups investigated differ while in reality these two groups do not differ. In other words, it is the chance or the probability of a false-positive conclusion. Under usual circumstances, alpha is fixed at 0.05, which indicates that a researcher desires a less than 5% chance of drawing a false-positive conclusion. The conclusion drawn is false, because positive. The P Value is the probability obtained of incorrectly accepting the alternate hypothesis. The P Value is compared to the the significance level α to determine whether the result is statistically significant. The lower the P Value, the lower the probability of obtaining that result if a null hypothesis were true.

Type I and type II errors

Type I error: A true null hypothesis is rejected. **Type II error:** A false null hypothesis is accepted.

Figure 1. Today's understanding of the relationship between Type I error and Type II error.

Power (1-Beta)

The type II error is also called beta and represents the chance or the probability to decide that the two groups investigated do not differ (no difference), while in reality these two groups do differ. In other words, it is the chance or the probability of a false-negative conclusion. The conclusion drawn is false, because negative. Usually, beta is set at a level of 0.20. In other words, a researcher desires a less than 20% chance of a false-negative conclusion. Nonetheless, for the calculation of the sample size, it is necessary to consider the following relationship.

$$\beta + \text{power} = 1 \quad (18)$$

Consequently, power is the complement of beta, i.e. $\text{power} = 1 - \beta$. Thus far, if beta is 0.20, then the power is 0.80 or 80%. The power indicates the probability or the chance to avoid a false-negative conclusion or, in other words, the probability to detect a specified effect, assumed that the same really exists.

What is very interesting is that today's understanding of the relationship between Type I error and Type II error excludes the possibility of a joint distribution between Type I error and Type II error, as demonstrated by figure ³³ 1. In other words, theoretically, it appears not to be possible that a null-

³³Serdar CC, Cihan M, Yücel D, Serdar MA. Sample size, power and effect size revisited: simplified and practical approaches in

hypothesis is false in reality (α) and that a statistical test tell us at the same time that a null-hypothesis is false (β) too. In the long run, this shortcoming may turn out to be unsustainable.

Table 8. Today's relationship between α and β

		R E S E A R C H		
		H ₀ is TRUE	H _A is TRUE	
R E A L I T Y	H ₀ is TRUE	$1 - \alpha$	α	1
	H _A is TRUE	β	$1 - \beta$	1
		$1 - \alpha + \beta$	$1 + \alpha - \beta$	2

pre-clinical, clinical and laboratory studies. *Biochem Med (Zagreb)*. 2021 Feb 15;31(1):010502. doi: 10.11613/BM.2021.010502. Epub 2020 Dec 15. PMID: 33380887; PMCID: PMC7745163.

3. Results

3.1. Without EBV infection, no MGUS

Mameli et al. ³⁴ published data on the relationship EBV and MGUS.

Theorem 1 (EBV and MGUS).

Null-hypothesis (H_0):

Without EBV infection, no MGUS is true.

Alternative-hypothesis (H_A):

Without EBV infection, no MGUS is not true.

Proof by direct proof. The data of Mameli et al. were re-analysed (see table 2). The causal relationship between EBV and MGUS is positive and statistically significant. The necessary condition (conditio sine qua non) relationship between EBV and MGUS is $p(\text{SINE}) = 0.96$ and significant. In other words, we must accept the null-hypothesis as true:

Without EBV infection, no MGUS (P Value = 0.00903844).

□

³⁴Mameli G, Fozza C, Niegowska M, Corda G, Ruda MF, Barraqueddu F, Dessì L, Podda L, Dore F, Sechi LA. Epstein-Barr virus infection is associated to patients with multiple myeloma and monoclonal gammopathy of undetermined significance. *Leuk Lymphoma*. 2017 Feb;58(2):466-469. doi: 10.1080/10428194.2016.1190976. Epub 2016 Jun 7. PMID: 27268403.

3.2. Without EBV infection, no MM

Mameli et al. ³⁵ published additional data on the relationship EBV and MM.

Theorem 2 (EBV and MM).

Null-hypothesis (H_0):

Without EBV infection, no MM is true.

Alternative-hypothesis (H_A):

Without EBV infection, no MM is not true.

Proof by direct proof. The data of Mameli et al. were re-analysed again (see table 3 and the fictive data of table 4). The causal relationship between EBV and MM is positive and statistically significant. Under conditions of unfair study design, the necessary condition (conditio sine qua non) relationship between EBV and MM is $p(\text{SINE}) = 0.94$ and statistically significant. In other words, we must accept the null-hypothesis as true:

Without EBV infection, no MM (P Value = 0.02533552).

□

³⁵Mameli G, Fozza C, Niegowska M, Corda G, Ruda MF, Barraqueddu F, Dessì L, Podda L, Dore F, Sechi LA. Epstein-Barr virus infection is associated to patients with multiple myeloma and monoclonal gammopathy of undetermined significance. *Leuk Lymphoma*. 2017 Feb;58(2):466-469. doi: 10.1080/10428194.2016.1190976. Epub 2016 Jun 7. PMID: 27268403.

3.3. *If EBV infection, then MM*

Mohammad Hadi Sadeghian et al. ³⁶ published data on the relationship EBV and MM.

Theorem 3 (EBV and MM).

Null-hypothesis (H_0):

If EBV infection, then MM is true.

Alternative-hypothesis (H_A):

If EBV infection, then MM is not true.

Proof by direct proof. The data of Sadeghian et al. were re-analysed (see table 5). The causal relationship between EBV and MM is positive and statistically significant. Under conditions of unfair study design, the sufficient condition (conditio per quam) relationship between EBV and MM is p (IMP) = 0.95 and statistically significant. In other words, we must accept the null-hypothesis as true:

If EBV infection (of bone marrow et cetera), then MM (P Value = 0.02873314).

□

³⁶Sadeghian MH, Ayatollahi H, Keramati MR, Memar B, Jamedar SA, Avval MM, Sheikhi M, Shaghayegh G. The association of Epstein-Barr virus infection with multiple myeloma. *Indian J Pathol Microbiol.* 2011 Oct-Dec;54(4):720-4. doi: 10.4103/0377-4929.91504. PMID: 22234097.

3.4. EBV infection is the cause of MM

Theorem 4 (EBV and MM).***Null-hypothesis (H_0):***

EBV infection and MM: no causal relationship.

Alternative-hypothesis (H_A):

EBV infection and MM: causal relationship.

Proof by direct proof. Mameli et al. provided evidence of a necessary condition relationship between EBV and MM (see table 3 and the fictive data of table 4). Sadeghian et al. demonstrated (see table 5) that there is a sufficient condition relationship between EBV and MM. Both study groups demonstrated a positive and statistically significant causal relationship between EBV and MM (see table 3 and the fictive data of table 4 and table 5). In other words, we must reject the null-hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis:

EBV is the cause of MM (P Value < 0.029).

□

4. Discussion

It has been some time since the first well-documented case of MM has been reported in 1844 by Samuel Solly.³⁷ Henry Bence Jones (1813–1873),³⁸ a well-known physician, described in the middle of the 19th century, that a grocer forty-seven years of age, excreted a large amount of protein.³⁹ Soon, Otto Kahler reported the case of Dr. Loos, one of the best known cases of multiple myeloma.⁴⁰ Based on these and other insights, meanwhile multiple myeloma is frequently found even in patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA).^{41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46} After all, Epstein-Barr virus has been identified as the cause of rheumatoid arthritis.⁴⁷ It is therefore not surprising, that the previous reports are explained by this 2018 year publication in its entirety logically and that the same publications provide additional⁴⁸ and indirect evidence for the theses published in this publication. In this regard, studies provided some slight evidence that EBV interferes with cellular DNA repair mechanisms. As a result, genetic changes in the infected cells are possible.^{49, 50} A B-cell lymphoid malignancy might initiate from a clone of EBV-infected B cells. We have to ask ourselves at this very moment whether EBV is a killer virus, a nature given and nature used weapon of mass destruction of human life? Viruses are able to lose and to gain genes. Therefore, viruses are not only life destroyer but creator of life and potentially new species too and essential drivers⁵¹ of evolution. In other word, answering the question question before might

³⁷Solly Samuel. Remarks on the pathology of mollities ossium; with cases. *Med Chir Trans.* 1844;27:435-498.8. doi: 10.1177/095952874402700129. PMID: 20895811; PMCID: PMC2116942.

³⁸Kyle RA, Steensma DP. History of multiple myeloma. *Recent Results Cancer Res.* 2011;183:3-23. doi: 10.1007/978-3-540-85772-3_1. PMID: 21509678.

³⁹Bence Jones H. On the new substance occurring in the urine of a patient with mollities ossium. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci.* 1848;138:55–62. doi:10.1098/rstl.1848.0003

⁴⁰Kahler, Otto. (1889). Zur symptomatologie des multiplen myeloms: Beobachtung von Albumosurie. *Prag. Med. Wochenschr.*, 13, 33-45.

⁴¹Cibere J, Sibley J, Haga M. Rheumatoid arthritis and the risk of malignancy. *Arthritis Rheum.* 1997 Sep;40(9):1580-6. doi: 10.1002/art.1780400906. PMID: 9324011.

⁴²Usnarska-Zubkiewicz L, Czarnecka M, Włodarczyk S, Nowak E. Reumatoidalne zapalenie stawów jako czynnik ryzyka w rozwoju szpiczaka plazmocytoowego [Rheumatoid arthritis as a risk factor for development of multiple myeloma]. *Pol Arch Med Wewn.* 1997 Mar;97(3):253-9. Polish. PMID: 9333771.

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be done like ever entirely according to the reader's own taste. Whatever such an answer may be, these findings stress among other the urgent need for an effective vaccine against EBV infection and equally against an EBV re-activation.

5. Conclusion

Taking all the previous aspects into consideration it is justified to conclude that

Epstein–Barr virus is the cause of multiple myeloma.

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

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Associated Data

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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